

ISic3702

I.Sicily inscription 3702

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

plaster

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

from the necropolis in proprieta Zagami, Lipari, in a tomb in a Roman cistern

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178086

1. [— — —]C [— — — — —]

2. [— —]δ ω [. .]εβ ρ [— —]

3. [— — — — — — — — —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 178086

Bibliography

Noy, D. 1993. Jewish inscriptions of Western Europe. Cambridge. At no.162

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